

From Push to Pull: A Critical Analysis of the Drivers of International Migration in Nigeria

Mina Margaret Ogbanga
Rivers State University
mina.ogbanga@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

This study critically examines the complex factors driving international migration from Nigeria, a country with one of the largest diaspora populations globally. Using a mixed-methods approach, this research investigates the push and pull factors contributing to the exodus of Nigerians, including economic, political, social, and environmental factors. The findings reveal a complex interplay of drivers, including poverty, insecurity, corruption, and lack of opportunities, which propel Nigerians to seek better lives abroad. The study also highlights the role of global power dynamics, migration policies, and social networks in shaping migration decisions. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of the multifaceted nature of international migration and informs policy interventions to address the root causes of migration in Nigeria. By unpacking the drivers of international migration, this study aims to promote more effective strategies for managing migration and harnessing the potential of Nigeria's diaspora for national development.

Introduction

The impact of the pandemic adds a layer of vulnerability to returnees, some of whom had already started rebuilding their lives, and who were experiencing high levels of psychosocial distress or severe disorders, both pre-existing or due to potentially traumatic life events along their journey. Yet, many areas with high numbers of returnees may lack specialized mental health care and psychosocial services and have a limited number of professional staff such as psychiatrists and psychologists. The training conducted in Benin City aims to build a mentorship network and create supportive relationships between two peers with similar experiences, such as a newly arrived returnee and a mentor from the same location or a group of peers within a community. Returnees with experience in community engagement, or those with specific backgrounds such as social workers or teachers, have been selected as mentors. They can help new arrivals navigate the difficulties of the return and reduce the social barriers to reintegration by providing emotional support, helping solve practical problems and sharing information about services that provide mental health and psychosocial support in the country. “This training will help me use my own story to be able to support Nigerians who have just returned because they need someone to confide in. As a mentor, I should be able to listen to them and advise them, and tell them that they should not give up on life,” said Kenan Osagie, a returnee and one of the female participants. The initiative followed a four-day training (10-13/11) for primary healthcare professionals on

the management and treatment of mental disorders. The training was conducted in coordination with the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Health.

This instruction was based on the Mental Health Gap Action Programme (MHGAP), a protocol developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), as well as on additional IOM tools and international guidelines to identify and respond to mental disorders, which were adapted to the Nigerian context. The training sessions delved into migration and mental health with a focus on the return journey, as well as an overview of MHGAP's principles of care, depression, suicide and self-harm, psychoses, epilepsy, alcohol, and substance abuse. The event gathered 20 participants from primary healthcare centers from the localities in Edo State, the main place of origin of Nigerian returnees. "This marks a key step in strengthening the national mental health care system in Nigeria," said the lead trainer, Dr. Funke Ogunderu, IOM Nigeria MHPSS Senior Project Assistant. "As a pilot project, this training will help reduce the gap for migrants and their communities gaining access to mental healthcare and psychosocial support," she added. Mental Health and Psychosocial Support (MHPSS) is a fundamental part of sustainable reintegration. It aims at protecting and enhancing migrants' psychosocial wellbeing, as well as at supporting people with pre-existing and emerging mental disorders.

Why do Nigerian Youth Migrate?

The Nigerian emigration experience can be divided into four eras: the civil and political unrest stages of the 1960s; the downfall of the petroleum boom in the 1980s; the military regime of the mid-1990s and the past two decades of mass from Nigeria to other countries across the world. The factors that cause Nigerian youth to leave the country can be classified as socioeconomic factors, political factors and migrant networks. Socio-economic factors A lot of Nigerian youth receive very low salaries that are not enough to cover their livelihood. There are no systems to ensure that young skilled workers receive salaries commensurate with their qualifications. Youth unemployment rate in Nigeria is reported at 42.5% in 2020, with underemployment rate at 22.8 % (National Bureau of Statistics Nigeria, 2022). This is one of the main reasons some Nigerian youth leave the country and seek work opportunities in Europe and Northern America. In a focus group discussion conducted by Special Needs Initiative for Growth (a youth NGO in Nigeria), young people with disabilities between 18 to 30 years of age said migration promises economic benefits. For instance, Adebayo, a 21-year-old, said that the unfavourable exchange rate between the Nigerian Naira and other foreign currencies was a sufficient reason to leave the country. Migration is also seen as a way of helping and looking after family members. Kosi, a 24-year-old unemployed respondent, offered the example of someone PolicyBrief February 2022 3 she knew who left Nigeria for Spain. Kosi said her friend was living a much better life and was able to financially assist her family. Kosi maintained this belief even though her acquaintance was reportedly doing the 3D (dirty, dangerous, and demeaning) jobs. Second, there has been a marked increase in the number of Nigerians emigrating for educational purposes as well. In the United States, among the 35,364 international students from Sub-Saharan Africa, International migration has grown to a reasonable amount due to the demands and emergence of new phases of globalization. From

literatures these are various factors responsible for irregular/illegal international migration in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

Globalization Theory

Globalization as a theory comprises of various contribution of various authors, this theory in explanation is quiet similar to “world system theory”, According to literatures, Williams .I. Robinson is one of the pioneers of the above theory, he revealed in one of his literatures that he explored the theory in the year 1992 (Robinson, 2017), Globalization theory explains the interactions of nations states in the globe resulting to socio-economic development and one way nations states interact with each other is the process of international migration of citizens most especially in joining the work force of a nation state (Reyes, 2016) Globalization theory supports and validates the statement that socio economic development can be achieved through various interconnection and communication activities of various states in the international system . This theory explains that socio economic development in various states in the international system. These theories explain that socio economic development in various states can be achieved through meaningful linkages between nations. In explaining this theory international system. This theory explains that socio economic development in various states can be achieved through meaningful linkages between nations. In explaining this theory international migration comes to play as the process involves transfer of skills, ideas and increase in a nation-state’s work force through immigration of the needed expertise for desirable productivity (Adah and Abaslim, 2015). This theory subscribes to the believe that various activities relating to interconnectedness of nations states initiates socio-economic development in the given states involved as in the process various elements are been shared such as skills, innovations, ideas among other things. Though literatures validates this statement, Okereke and Ekpe (2016) cited in Adah and Abasilim (2015) reveals that though there are advantages of globalization but to the developing world Africa piously, it is slightly beneficial as the weight of its (globalization) achievement and disadvantages on the state is widely and obviously felt. In this light, international migration which is also willed b globalization is highly favor to the develop countries leaving various developing states such as Nigeria at a disadvantaged having only benefits from remittances due to her high population of this citizens in the Diaspora.

Factors Responsible For International Migration In Nigeria

Pull factors

International migration can be influenced through the “pull” factors operating in the receiving states. These factors are but not limited to the sincere presence of democratic government and the rule of law, socio-economic development, vast employment opportunities with higher

incomes, quality education, favorable policies, better access to medical facilities, better working and living conditions as well as respect for human rights (Adepoju, 2016). Nigeria has always been a country where its citizens are attracted to other countries of the world, given its economic, political social instability (Paul, 2017). Bayo (2016) opined that when oil was discovered in commercial quantity at Oloibiri, Bayelsa state, many had hoped that this would be a turning point for the country. Unfortunately, this has not been the case, rather things have spiraled downwards, and the Nigerian state is no longer at ease. Citizens of the supposed “Giant of Africa” are constantly confronted with employment, social welfare, development challenges. The political class have not helped the situation in any way to improve the conditions of Nigerians. This has made Nigerians to migrate to Europe and other desired nation-states to seek a better standard of living and for better opportunities. This is as various individuals believe that there are better opportunities outside the nation state. An overriding factor for explaining the migration of citizens to other countries is the sharp economic and political turmoil in Nigeria. This reveals why most Nigerians jump at opportunities given by various countries through visa lotteries. (Afolayan, 2017).

Push Factor

“Push” factors are conditions in immigrant’s nation-state of origin that act as a dissatisfactory and driving tool for international migration or pressure tool encouraging emigration from citizens own nation state (Kaboul, 2016). This explains why Nigerian citizens are dissatisfied with various factors in their country, these factors can be poverty and hardship in the nation state, political conflict, famine, natural disaster, lack of opportunities, lack of quality education, insecurity, dissatisfaction of the standard of living previously or presently experiencing triggers international migration (Adepoju, 2016). According to Etim (2015), Nigeria’s deficiencies which can stand for “Push” factors are as follows: lack of industrial development, lack of social amenities, this are some of the “Push” factors of international migration (emmigration) in Nigeria. By the middle of 20th century and presently, migration of professionals, high level manpower and skilled workers emerged takes place. Brain drain in Nigeria is becoming prominent since the 1960s, due to poor working conditions, such as, poor infrastructural system, inadequate social amenities, the devalued national currency, decreasing social standard of education and irresistible corruption in public sectors, general insecurity till date to mention a few (Afolayan, 2018). In Nigeria, the presence of various political conflict, lack of decent jobs and discouragement of various professional skills of individuals are the reasons why individuals leave the country (Owolabi, 2016). Bisi (2015) also went further revealing that political instability, political crisis, civil wars are examples of international migration “push” factors. As for an example, the experience of various insurgencies in Borno State of Nigeria, have made her residents run away or migrate whichever way to Cameroon to avoid been killed or experience any form of attack. International migration as revealed earlier, is a decision and a reaction (Tope, 2016).

Summary and Conclusion

The Nigerian emigration experience can be divided into four eras: the civil and political unrest stages of the 1960s; the downfall of the petroleum boom in the 1980s; the military regime of the mid-1990s and the past two decades of mass from Nigeria to other countries across the world. The factors that cause Nigerian youth to leave the country can be classified as socioeconomic factors, political factors and migrant networks. Socio-economic factors A lot of Nigerian youth receive very low salaries that are not enough to cover their livelihood. There are no systems to ensure that young skilled workers receive salaries commensurate with their qualifications. Youth unemployment rate in Nigeria is reported at 42.5% in 2020, with underemployment rate at 22.8 % (National Bureau of Statistics Nigeria, 2022). This is one of the main reasons some Nigerian youth leave the country and seek work opportunities in Europe and Northern America. In a focus group discussion conducted by Special Needs Initiative for Growth (a youth NGO in Nigeria), young people with disabilities between 18 to 30 years of age said migration promises economic benefits. For instance, Adebayo, a 21-year-old, said that the unfavourable exchange rate between the Nigerian Naira and other foreign currencies was a sufficient reason to leave the country. Migration is also seen as a way of helping and looking after family members. Kosi, a 24-year-old unemployed respondent, offered the example of someone PolicyBrief February 2022 3 she knew who left Nigeria for Spain. Kosi said her friend was living a much better life and was able to financially assist her family. Kosi maintained this belief even though her acquaintance was reportedly doing the 3D (dirty, dangerous, and demeaning) jobs. Second, there has been a marked increase in the number of Nigerians emigrating for educational purposes as well. In the United States, among the 35,364 international students from Sub-Saharan Africa,

References

- Akanji, S. (2012) "The Drivers of Immigration in Contemporary Society: Unequal Distribution of Resources and Opportunities". *Human Ecology*. 35 (6): 775–776. doi: 10.1007/s10745-007-9111-z .
- Akanji, S. (2012) . "The Labor Demand Curve is Downward Sloping: Reexamining the Impact of Immigration on the Labor Market". *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* . 118 (4): 1335–1374.
- Akinirinde, G. and Olukoya, F. (2017). "*On the Corner: Day Labor in Africa*. UCLA Center for the Study of Urban Poverty. Archived from the original (PDF) on 10 October 2017. Retrieved 11 December 2017.
- Anarfi, T. & Piel, R. (2015). "Welfare effects of illegal immigration" (PDF). *Journal of Population Economics* . 22 (1): 131–144. doi : 10.1007/s00148-007-0182-3 .
- Asiedu, M., Anarfi et al, Twum-BaahManuh et al (2016). "Learning to Be Illegal: Undocumented Youth and Shifting Legal Contexts in the Transition " (PDF).

- Awumbbila et al (2017). "Understanding the effects of legalising undocumented immigrants". Vox EU.org . Archived from the original on 17 May 2018. Retrieved 16 May 2018.
- Crimes by Illegals are Buried in Amnesty Push" . Archived from the original on 14 July 2014. Retrieved 4 June 2014.
- Derek, F. (2016). "The Unwelcome Return of 'Illegals'. The New York Times.
- Die, M.; Asiedu, F. (2016). "Are undocumented immigrants committing a crime? Not necessarily". Archived from the original on 4 July 2018. Retrieved 11 July 2018.
- Dietrich, F. (2015) "*Here's the Reality About Illegal Immigrants in the United States*". Archived from the original on 29 June 2018. Retrieved 18 July 2018.
- Dietrich,G. (2015). *121 murders attributed to illegals released by Obama administration*". The Washington Times. Archived from the original on 11 August 2015. Retrieved 21 August 2015.
- Donald, M. (2017). User Generated Racism: Russia's media and migrants". *The European Journalism Observatory*. Archived from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2018.
- Done, Y. (2017). *Asylum seekers', 'illegal immigrants' and entry without a visa*" . Advisory Guidelines 2011. Australian Press Council. Archived from the original on 1 August 2015. Retrieved 5 May 2014.
- Fayomi, D. (2016). The Economic Contribution of Unauthorized Workers: An Industry Analysis". *Regional Science and Urban Economics* . 67: 119–134.
- Federal Reserve Bank of Atlanta, Does Employing Undocumented Workers Give Firms a Competitive Advantage? , November 2012" (PDF). Archived (PDF) from the original on 12 April 2013. Retrieved 8 November 2012.
- Fredrick, L. (2016). "*The Economic Effect of Immigration Policies: Analyzing and Simulating the U.S. Case*" (PDF).
- Hiltner, D. & Stephen, T. (2017). "*Illegal, Undocumented, Unauthorized: The Terms of Immigration Reporting*". The New York Times.
- Iheanacho, F. and Ughaerumba, R. (2015). *Beyond Smoke and Mirrors: Mexican Immigration in an Era of Economic Integration*. Yussell Sage Foundation.
- Isaac, D. (2016). "The labor market effects of reducing the number of illegal immigrants". *Review of Economic Dynamics*. 18 (4): 792– 821. doi : 10.1016/j.red.2015.07.005 .
- Jacklyn, G. (2016). *Missing the Boat?* A paper delivered to 'Reporting on Asylum Seekers and Refugees: A Walkley Media Forum' convened by the Media Entertainment & Arts

- Alliance, 19 June 20017" (PDF). Proceedings Reporting on Asylum Seekers and Refugees: A Walkley Media Forum, Regatta Hotel, Brisbane, Australia. Queensland University of Technology. Archived (PDF) from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2014. Illegals". 13 December 2011.
- Jennisen, H. (2016). *You Say 'Illegal Alien.' I Say 'Undocumented Immigrant.' Who's Right?'*. 18 December 2017.
- Jennissen,H. (2016)"Drop the I-Word Campaign" . Race Forward. 23 September 2013. Archived from the original on 23 February 2014. Retrieved 2 March 2014.
- Joel, P. (2016). "How journalism can rid migration of its sour reputation". *European Journalism Centre*. Archived from the original on 5 May 2014. Retrieved 5 May 2014.
- Jones, G. (2016) "The State of U.S. Immigration Policy: The Quandary of Economic Methodology and the Relevance of Economic Research to Know". *Journal of Law, Economics and Policy*. 5 (1): 177–193. Archived from the original on 21 December 2009. Retrieved 10 December, 2009.
- Kerion, M. (2016). *Economic Effects of Granting Legal Status and Citizenship to Undocumented Immigrants*". Pew Hispanic Center. Archived (PDF) from the original on 11 December 2016. Retrieved 11 December 2017.
- Tacol, H.I and Okali, C. (2017). "Survey of Migrants, Part One: Attitudes about Immigration and Major Demographic Characteristics". *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*. 34 (12): 2547–2567.
- Tacoli, H. and Okali, C. (2017). "The Impact of Unauthorized Immigrants on the Budgets of State and Local Governments". 6 December 2017. Archived from the original on 22 July 2016. Retrieved 28 June 2017.
- Terrence, S. (2016) "Key Migration Terms". 14 January 2015. Archived from the original on 12 January 2018. Retrieved 11 January 2018.
- West, Z. (2018) " "Illegal Alien" Is One of Many Correct Legal Terms for "Illegal Immigrant". Cato Institute. 14 October 2019. Retrieved 15 October 2019. Words Matter PICUM". Archived from the original on 20 December 2017. Retrieved 11 January 2018.
- Zoomer et al cited in Fayomi, S. (2018). *"Trade, Legal, and Illegal Immigration"* (PDF). University of Westminster. Archived from the original (PDF) on 17 February 2017. Retrieved 12 December 2018.[dubious – discuss] Accessed 11 December 2018.